

Table S1. Analysis of variance of eight traits in the sorghum BCNAM population across three environments (Kobo, Meiso, and Sheraro). Phenotypic traits include number of leaves (NL), head exertion (HE), leaf senescence (LS), number of tillers (NT), count of plants per plot (CPP), single plant-based grain yield (SGY), plot-based grain yield (PGY), and 1000-seed weight (TSW).

Trait	Term	DF	SS	MS	F	<i>P</i> value
LS	Environment	1	114.4	114.36	117.418	< 2e-16
	Family	11	77.5	7.05	7.235	3.70E-12
	Genotype	1147	1401	1.22	1.254	1.38E-05
	Family*Environment	11	64.8	5.89	6.047	9.12E-10
	Genotype*Environment	1015	1256.4	1.24	1.271	8.95E-06
	Residuals	1650	1607	0.97		
NL	Environment	2	24694	12347	15591.13	< 2e-16
	Family	11	146	13	16.717	< 2e-16
	Genotype	1159	2029	2	2.211	< 2e-16
	Family*Environment	19	53	3	3.538	3.35E-07
	Genotype*Environment	2040	2616	1	1.619	< 2e-16
	Residuals	2693	2133	1		
HE	Environment	1	10981	10981	616.792	< 2e-16
	Family	11	6424	584	32.8	< 2e-16
	Genotype	1147	42996	37	2.105	< 2e-16
	Family*Environment	11	1286	117	6.567	8.27E-11
	Genotype*Environment	1015	19244	19	1.065	0.131
	Residuals	1650	30146	18		
NT	Environment	1	934.5	934.5	889.235	< 2e-16
	Family	11	122.3	11.1	10.581	< 2e-16
	Genotype	1147	1344.9	1.2	1.116	0.0215
	Family*Environment	11	101	9.2	8.734	3.22E-15
	Genotype*Environment	1015	1316.9	1.3	1.235	8.22E-05
	Residuals	1650	1733.9	1		
CPP	Environment	2	60633	30316	7574	< 2e-16
	Family	11	2158	196	49	< 2e-16
	Genotype	1159	7494	6.5	1.6	< 2e-16
	Family*Environment	19	178	9.4	2.3	8.41E-04
	Genotype*Environment	2040	8558	4.2	1.05	0.12
	Residuals	2694	10783	4.0		

Trait	Term	DF	SS	MS	F	<i>P</i> value
SGY	Environment	2	618871	309435	892.123	< 2e-16
	Family	11	83674	7607	21.931	< 2e-16
	Genotype	1159	563910	487	1.403	1.73E-12
	Family*Environment	19	53801	2832	8.164	< 2e-16
	Genotype*Environment	2040	992319	486	1.402	< 2e-16
	Residuals	2690	933034	347		
PGY	Environment	2	10322143	5161072	133.9528	< 2e-16
	Family	11	9599721	872702	22.6505	< 2e-16
	Genotype	1159	62861091	54237	1.4077	1.00e-16
	Family*Environment	19	5359413	282074	7.3211	< 2e-16
	Genotype*Environment	2040	102681425	50334	1.3064	4.87e-11
	Residuals	2694	103797235			
TSW	Environment	2	106473	53237	3634.438	< 2e-16
	Family	11	9204	837	57.12	< 2e-16
	Genotype	1159	31528	27	1.857	< 2e-16
	Family*Environment	19	3330	175	11.965	< 2e-16
	Genotype*Environment	2040	45577	22	1.525	< 2e-16
	Residuals	2690	39403	15		

Table S2. Sorghum BCNAM trait means within each environment.

Trait§	Unit	Kobo	Meiso	Sheraro
HE	cm	1.29	2.91/6.15‡	
LS	Score (1-5)	2.49	2.81	
NL	count	8.76	9.95	13.60
NT	count	0.67	0.21	
SGY	gram	62.83	54.64	38.20
CPP	count	8.45	9.08	15.67
PGY	gram	340.39	522.98	601.99
TSW	gram	29.48	20.80	19.67
DF	days	78.15	85.05	64.99
DM	days	127.04	122.66	90.22
GFP	days	48.89	37.61	25.22

§HE: head exertion, LS: leaf senescence, NL: number of leaves, NT: number of tillers, SGY: single plant-based grain yield, CPP: count of plants per plot, PGY: plot-based grain yield, TSW: 1000-seed weight, DF: days to 50% flowering, DM: days to maturity, GFP: grain filling period, which was calculated by subtracting DM by DF.

‡Since HE at Meiso exhibited severe left-skewed distribution, Box-Cox transformation was conducted to transform original data to approximately normal distribution. 2.91 is the trait mean value obtained using Box-Cox transformed data, 6.15 is the trait mean value obtained using original data.

Table S3. Rank-based correlation coefficients (Kendall's τ) for the same trait across environments. Phenotypic traits include days to flowering (DF), days to maturity (DM), plant height (PH), number of leaves (NL), head exertion (HE), leaf senescence (LS), number of tillers (NT), count of plants per plot (CPP), single plant-based grain yield (SGY), plot-based grain yield (PGY), and 1000-seed weight (TSW).

	Kobo vs Meiso	Kobo vs Sheraro	Meiso vs Sheraro
DF	0.16	0.01	0.01
DM	0.11	-0.01	0.01
HE	0.23	NA	NA
LS	0.02	NA	NA
NL	0.26	0.00	0.02
NT	0.03	NA	NA
PH	0.25	0.02	0.03
SGY	0.08	0.02	0.03
TSW	0.15	0.04	0.07
CPP	0.11	0.00	0.00
PGY	0.09	0.03	0.04

NA: data not available.